

1 **Sod1-3 activation in human cells occurs during acute infection.**

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7 A mutation in Sod1 is the most classically understood cause of Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis.
8 Endogenous changes in superoxide dismutase expression are described across biologic setting, and more
9 significant stimulus-dependent induction of Sod1, Sod2 and Sod3 is also described. Here we combine
10 systems biologic approaches across discipline to understand and define a functional role for superoxide
11 dismutase induction in normal cellular function. We distinguish this normal function which is likely
12 associated with housekeeping activities in the cell from one apparently required for during the primary
13 phase of immune defense following cellular infection with a bacterium.

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